

Influence Of Academic Qualifications, Lecturer Competencies And Curriculum On Student Learning Achievement Through Teaching Factory

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 01, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: August 02, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Teaching Factory, Lecturer Competence, Curriculum, Learning Achievement</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6954101</p>	<p><i>Entering the era of disruption and the era of the industrial revolution 4.0, universities, especially Polytechnics, have a fairly high challenge in producing graduates who are adaptable to the development of science and technology. The academic qualifications of lecturers at the Polytechnic of the former Pekalongan residency are still not linear as much as 30% and student learning achievement is less than optimal This study proves that the use of the variable teaching factory mediator is very effective for use in learning at the Polytechnic in Central Java. Future research can be developed on the influence of teaching factory management variables on the soft skills and hard skills of students at the Polytechnic. This research methodology uses a quantitative research approach. The research subject is a lecturer at a Polytechnic who has a teaching factory in the Karisedenan area of Pekalongan, Central Java. Data analysis using path analysis with SPSS 20.</i></p>

Introduction

1.1 Conceptual or Theoretical Framework

Higher education is entering a new era, namely the era of disruption and the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 and the era of society 5.0. Universities are required to be a source of knowledge, academic resources and can produce graduates who are competitive and adaptable. Polytechnic is one form of higher education which is a vocational-based education. Entering the era of disruption and the era of the industrial revolution 4.0, universities, especially Polytechnics, have a fairly high challenge in producing graduates who are adaptable to the development of science and technology. The need for professionalism of lecturers and the adequacy of learning facilities on campus is one of the main determining factors to produce quality graduates. In this condition, the lecturer is like a driving force related to scientific and academic activities.

The law requires university lecturers to have at least a master's degree. The law states that primary and secondary education educators are required to have at least a bachelor's degree. Meanwhile, to educate at the undergraduate level of academic education, at least have a bachelor's degree (S2), while for postgraduate programs are doctorates (S3) and professors.

Yasir (2018), lecturer performance will affect the community's demands on the quality of college graduates. Universities are required to produce workers and experts. Higher education is expected to produce graduates who can work independently, have the knowledge, skills and attitudes to compete widely.

The quality of university graduates such as Polytechnics is still judged to have not met the government's expectations. This is because the learning process at the Polytechnic is still conventional. Learning infrastructure is still limited, even from observations in several Polytechnics, the conditions of Polytechnic laboratories are not adequate when compared to laboratories in vocational high schools (SMK). Teaching factory is the government's solution to the success of vocational education. Teaching factory which is focused on vocational education is very relevant to be implemented in Polytechnic education. The results of the study indicate that there is effectiveness in increasing student learning outcomes or achievements in vocational schools. Mustari, et al (2017) and Ahmad F et al (2015) prove that teaching factory learning is very effective in improving student learning achievement. There have been several Pekalongan Residency Polytechnics that have implemented teaching factories in recent years, but there has been no study on the important role of teaching factories at the Pekalongan Residency Polytechnic.

The problem that occurs today is that there is still a miss match between what is learned at school or college with the business world and the industrial world. This means that the learning materials at the Polytechnic are not in accordance with the needs of the world of work, so it is necessary to improve the quality, relevance and revitalization of Polytechnic education in forming qualified and highly competitive human resources. Thus, a link and match is created between learning on campus and the needs of IDUKA (business world industry and the world of work). The academic qualifications of lecturers at the Polytechnic of the former Pekalongan

residency are still not linear as much as 30% and student learning achievement is less than optimal. have not been able to apply properly because of difficulties in linking and matching with industry in achieving industry-based learning. Not all of the teaching factories at the ex-residence of Pekalongan Polytechnic have, and there has been no study on the effectiveness of learning at the ex-residential Polytechnic of Pekalongan; Pekalongan has not met expectations, this can be seen from the low academic and academic achievements of students at the local and national levels.

1.2 Related Research

There are still polytechnics in the former Pekalongan residency area that implement learning that is not in accordance with the competency-based curriculum because of the limited adequate infrastructure. Ahmad Fa et al (2015) stated that in his research, the teaching factory learning model provided an increase in student achievement motivation. Suryabrata, S (2006: 297), achievement can also be defined as follows: "the value is the final formulation that can be given by the teacher regarding the progress/achievement of student learning during a certain period". So, achievement is the result of students' efforts during a certain period of doing activities. According to Hutabarat (1995: 11-12), learning outcomes are divided into four groups, namely: (1) Knowledge; (2) Ability; (3) Habits and skills; (4) attitude. Ngalim Purwanto (2010: 107), learning achievement is influenced by factors: (1) individual internal factors (physiological and psychological factors of students); (2) individual external factors (environment, curriculum, teachers, infrastructure, learning media, management). These factors greatly affect the quality of graduates and student learning outcomes.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

This study proves that the use of the variable teaching factory mediator is very effective for use in learning at the Polytechnic in Central Java. Future research can be developed on the influence of teaching factory management variables on the soft skills and hard skills of students at the Polytechnic.

1. Methods

2.1 Research Model

The research design that is used as a guide in this research is quantitative positivism with the research step (design) of the path analysis model. The design of this research is quantitative research through Path analysis model approach.

2.2. Participants

This research was conducted at the Polytechnic in the Pekalongan residency area which has a teaching factory. The population of this research is Polytechnic lecturers who have a linear Master's degree and teach at least 2 years. at least 2 years. The error rate in this study was 5%, the confidence interval was 95% and the population was 310 lecturers. Based on the Harry King Nomogram formula is as follows: the calculation of the sample in this study is $0.42 \times 310 \times 1.195 = 156.589$. Then obtained a minimum sample of 156,589 lecturers, rounded up to 156 lecturers for research data collection. (Pull from the number 156 past the 5% error level, then a point will be found above the number 40. The point is approximately 2, for an error of 5% it means the 95% confidence level so that the multiplier = 1.195). So the number of samples in this study were 156 lecturers.

2.3. Data Collection Tools

Data collection in this study was carried out using an instrument in the form of a questionnaire that had been tested for validity and reliability. The questionnaire was made based on the Likert scale, which is a statement followed by 5 answer choices that indicate the levels achieved by the ex-residential Polytechnic of Pekalongan, Central Java, from the lowest to the highest level.

2.4. Data Collection Process

The researcher made a questionnaire which was developed from the determination of variables related to student learning achievement, namely academic qualifications, lecturer competencies, curriculum, teaching factory at the former Pekalongan Residency Polytechnic. Data collection for each variable in this study was carried out using research tools made by researchers. In the form of a questionnaire which was then tested for validity and reliability. Instrument Validity Test using SPSS 16 for windows program. The questionnaire was made based on the Likert scale, which is a question followed by 5 answer choices that indicate the levels achieved by the respondents from the lowest to the highest level.

2.5. Data Analysis

In carrying out multiple regression analysis, the assumption test is carried out first including the normality test, linearity test, multicollinearity test and heteroscedasticity test with the help of SPSS 16. Results

Table 1. Summary of Research Results Direct and Indirect Effects

No	Variable	Direct/Simultaneous Effect	Direct Influence X1,X2 & Y→Z	Indirect Influence X1 & X2 -to Z by	Simultaneous Effect X1 & X2→Z
		Against Teaching			

		Factory		way of Y	
1	Lecturer Competence (X1)	0,273 19,9%	0,090 13,4%	0,161	14,8 %
2	Curriculum (X2)	0,212 17,3%	0,06 9,9%	0,125	
3	Teaching Factory(Y)	23,3 %	0,591 40,9 %	-	-

Based on the table and figure above, it can be explained that the results of statistical analysis obtained the coefficient of the influence of lecturer competence and curriculum on teaching factory learning of 0.273 (19.9%) and 0.212 (17.35). This means that the teaching factory variable will increase by 0.273 if the lecturer's competence variable increases by 1%. The lecturer competence variable has a direct influence of 19.9% on the teaching factory variable. Furthermore, the teaching factory variable will increase by 0.212 if the curriculum variable has an increase of 1%. The curriculum variable has a direct effect of 17.5% on the teaching factory variable.

Empirically these two variables contribute to supporting teaching factory learning at the Polytechnic. Polytechnics need lecturers who have qualified competencies in order to transfer knowledge and knowledge as well as hard skills and social skills.

2. Discussion

The Ministry of National Education (2002) suggests that the competency-based curriculum has the following characteristics; (1) emphasize the achievement of student competencies both individually and classically; (2) oriented to learning outcomes and diversity; (3) delivery of learning using varied approaches and methods; (4) learning resources are not only lecturers, but also learning resources in an effort to master or achieve a competency. The curriculum taught at Polytechnics is different from universities that are not based on vocational (vocational). This is what makes Polytechnics demand a standardized competency-based curriculum. In addition to the curriculum, the variable competence of lecturers is an important factor in achieving educational goals at the Polytechnic.

Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 37 of 2009 concerning lecturers stipulates that a lecturer can receive an educator certificate after going through a competency test in the form of a portfolio assessment that assesses the academic and professional experience of the lecturer. Lecturers are pioneers in providing transfer of knowledge and skills to students.

Based on this research, it shows that the curriculum and the competence of the lecturers make a significant contribution to the teaching factory. The variable of lecturer competence and curriculum has a simultaneous influence on the teaching factory by 23.3%. This shows that the existence of a good, quality curriculum and supported by competent lecturers will have a positive influence on improving the teaching factory. Students will feel comfortable and motivated in learning because learning activities have been well managed. Learning that has been designed starts from good planning, organizing, acting and controlling.

This study supports previous research Mustari, Sudana, M., Suprpto, E. (2017) that the teaching factory learning model is very appropriate for vocational education.

Direct Influence of Lecturer Competence, Curriculum, Teaching Factory on Student Achievement

Based on the table and figure above, it can be explained that the results of statistical analysis obtained coefficient values of the influence of lecturer competence and curriculum on student achievement of 0.09 (13.4%) and 0.06 (9.9%). This means that the student learning achievement variable will increase by 0.09 if the

lecturer's competence variable has an increase of 1%. The variable of lecturer competence has a direct effect of 13.4% on the variable of student achievement. Furthermore, the teaching factory variable will increase by 0.06 if the curriculum variable has an increase of 1%. The curriculum variable has a direct effect of 9.9% on the student achievement variable.

Empirically these two variables contribute to supporting student achievement at the Polytechnic, although it is still below 10%. Polytechnics need lecturers who have qualified competencies in order to transfer knowledge and knowledge as well as hard skills and social skills. Nana Sudjana (2005: 22) learning achievement consists of 3 domains, namely: (a) Cognitive domain; (2) Affective domain. Students must have mastery of these three aspects/domains in order to become human beings who are always adaptable to the times. Entering the 21st century and the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 requires students to have solid skills and are always adaptable to global developments. Competencies and curricula as described above are very much needed by polytechnics in producing graduates needed by the community, IDUKA (business world industry) and the state.

This study proves that the competence of lecturers and the curriculum has an important role in student-shared learning.

Indirect Effect of Lecturer Competence, Curriculum, on Student Achievement Through Teaching Factory

Based on the table and figure above, it can be explained that the results of statistical analysis obtained the coefficient of the indirect effect of lecturer competence on student learning achievement of 0.161. This means that the student learning achievement variable will increase by 0.116 if the lecturer's competence variable increases by 1%. The lecturer competence variable has an indirect influence coefficient of 0.125 on the student learning achievement variable. This means that the student learning achievement variable will increase by 0.125 if the lecturer's competence variable increases by 1%. The simultaneous effect of variables X1 (lecturer competence) and X2 (curriculum) on Z (student learning achievement) through Y (teaching factory) is 14.8%. The direct effect of teaching factory has an influence value of 0.591 with an effect on summary of 40.9%.

This author's research proves that the use of the variable teaching factory mediator can improve the achievement of Polytechnic students because the value of indirect influence is greater than the value of direct influence. The value of the coefficient of competence of lecturers is directly 0.09 to 0.161 (an increase of 0.07). The coefficient value of the curriculum variable was originally 0.06 to 0.125 (an increase of 0.065). This means that the teaching factory variable contributes significantly to student achievement. The simultaneous influence of the variable competence of lecturers and curriculum has an influence value of 14.8%.

The teaching factory has been proven to contribute or contribute to the learning that is followed by students with very significant achievements. The influence of 40.9% has a good and high value to be a solution in implementing learning at the Polytechnic. Learning management in the teaching factory model provides learning in real companies/industry. Students are provided with a pattern of working in a company based on standard operating procedures (SOPs). The teaching factory learning model equips students with organizational management, leadership, administration, financial governance and conflict management. The teaching factory provides a new learning direction in developing the quality of graduates. The component of lecturer competence and curriculum supported by the teaching factory learning model will have a positive influence on increasing student learning achievement. Qualified and adaptable Polytechnic graduates will make getting a job easier.

This supports previous research, Mustari et al. (2017) and Ahmad F et.al (2015), Ahmad, F.A, Hidayat, D, Suherman, A. 2015 proving that teaching factory learning is very effective in improving student achievement.

3. Conclusion

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that: (1) there is a significant positive direct effect of lecturer competence on the teaching factory with a coefficient value of 0.273 and the percentage value of the effect is 19.9%; (2) there is a significant positive direct influence of the curriculum on the teaching factory with a coefficient value of 0.212 and the percentage value of the effect is 17.3%; (3) there is a significant positive direct influence of lecturer competence on student learning achievement with a coefficient value of 0.09 and the percentage value of the effect is 13.4%; (4) there is a significant positive direct effect of the curriculum on student learning achievement with a coefficient value of 0.06 and the percentage value of the effect is 9.9%; (5) there is a significant positive direct influence of teaching factory on student learning achievement with a coefficient value of 0.591 and the percentage value of the effect 40.9%; (6) there is a significant positive indirect effect of lecturer competence on student learning achievement through the teaching factory variable of 0.161. The indirect effect is greater than the direct effect ($0.161 > 0.09$); (7) there is a significant positive indirect effect of the curriculum on student achievement through the teaching factory variable of 0.125. The indirect effect is greater than the direct effect ($0.125 > 0.06$).

This study proves that the use of the variable teaching factory mediator is very effective for use in learning at the Polytechnic in Central Java.

4. Recommendation

Future research can be developed on the influence of teaching factory management variables on the soft skills and hard skills of students at the Polytechnic. Polytechnics develop teaching learning factory to improve the competence of lecturers. Further develop industry-based curriculum and encourage polytechnic lecturers to improve qualifications according to the required competencies in learning the teaching factory model. Teaching factory recommended as a mediator variable in competency development lecturers to increase student learning achievement.

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